

Preliminary Phytochemical and Antimicrobial Screening of Seed and Coat of (*C. Sinensis*) Sweet Orange

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Abstract— Citrus fruits, particularly sweet oranges (*Citrus sinensis*), are widely consumed due to their nutritional and medicinal properties. The phytochemical screening of the methanolic extract of *C. sinensis* seed and coat of this study revealed the presence of various bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and phenols. The results of antimicrobial activity of the extracts of seed and coat of citrus *sinensis* on *Aspergillus niger*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* showed various degrees activities. The results of zone of inhibition of the seed extract of *Citrus Sinensis* against *Aspergillus Niger*, *Escherichia Coli* and *Staphylococcus Aureus* at 100mg/ml dose showed 2.0mm, 1.9mm, and 2.0mm at 100mg/ml concentration respectively as shown in table 2. The result of zone of inhibition of the coat extract of citrus *sinensis* against *Aspergillus Niger*, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus Aureus* at 100mg/ml dose showed 1.8mm, 1.6mm, and 1.7mm respectively as shown in table 4.2. The results showed that the seed and coat of citrus *sinensis* extracts has a minimum inhibitory concentration of 25mg/ml and 50mg/ml on *Aspergillus Niger*, *Escherichia Coli*, and *Staphylococcus Aureus* respectively shown in table 3. The results showed that the seed and coat extracts of citrus *sinensis* is microbiocidal to *Aspergillus Niger*, *Escherichia Coli* and *Staphylococcus Aureus* at a concentration of 50mg/ml and 100mg/ml shown in table 4. These findings support the potential use of *C. sinensis* extracts as a natural antimicrobial agent.

Keywords- Citrus fruit, *C. sinensis*, Antimicrobial agent, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer properties

I. INTRODUCTION

Plants have been a source of medicinal compounds for centuries, contributing to traditional medicine and modern drug discovery. Among these, phytochemicals, bioactive compounds derived from plants, have attracted significant attention due to their therapeutic potentials. These compounds often exhibit diverse biological activities, including antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer properties (Gurib-Fakim, 2006).

Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck (sweet orange) is the world's most widely grown and commercialized citrus specie. The fruit of *C. sinensis* is mostly recognized for its vitamin C content and is also an important source of other phytochemicals such as phenolics and carotenoids which are reputed to have health benefits. The sweet orange fruit is usually eaten whole or processed into juice after the peeling of the external rind (Ajayi and Ajibade, 2009). This peeling process leads to the generation of substantial wastes. Sweet orange (*C. sinensis*) is the world's most commonly cultivated fruit tree. It belongs to the Rutaceae family which comprises mandarins, limes, lemons, grapefruits, sour and sweet orange. Citrus fruits are of immense economic value; occupying the top position in fruit production. Orange trees are widely cultivated in tropical and subtropical climates for the sweet fruit, which is peeled or cut (to avoid the bitter rind) and eaten whole, or processed to extract orange juice. Citrus fruits are known to contain substantial quantities of vitamin C, a potent water-soluble vitamin essential for healthy living.

Given the increasing problem of antibiotic resistance, the exploration of natural products as alternative antimicrobial agents has gained momentum (Sofowora, 2006). This study

aims to perform a preliminary phytochemical and antimicrobial screening of the seed and coat of *C. sinensis*, as the plant may offer novel compounds effective against a range of microbial pathogens.

The rise of antibiotic-resistant pathogens poses a significant challenge to global public health. Traditional antibiotics are becoming less effective, necessitating the exploration of new, natural sources of antimicrobial agents. However, the phytochemical properties and antimicrobial activities of *C. sinensis*, especially its seed and coat, remain largely unstudied. Therefore, this research aims to address the gap in knowledge by investigating the bioactive compounds and antimicrobial properties of *C. sinensis*.

The need for new antimicrobial agents is urgent due to the global rise of multidrug-resistant pathogens. Plants are a well-known source of bioactive compounds, in particular, are recognized for their rich phytochemical profiles. *C. sinensis*, an underutilized legume, may possess compounds with significant antimicrobial activity. Studying the phytochemicals present in the seed and seed coat of *C. sinensis* could lead to the identification of novel bioactive compounds. Additionally, the findings could contribute to the promotion of this legume as a source of not only nutritional value but also medicinal properties.

This research is justified by the potential discovery of novel antimicrobial compounds from a locally available, yet underexplored, plant source. Moreover, the results could encourage further research into the medicinal uses of *C. sinensis*, potentially leading to its application in the treatment of infectious diseases.

A. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The Aim of this study is to investigate the preliminary phytochemical composition and antimicrobial activities of the seed and coat of *C. sinensis*.

The specific objectives are to identify the phytochemical constituents present in the seed and coat of *C. sinensis*, to assess the antimicrobial activity of extracts from the seed and coat against selected bacterial and fungal pathogens and to compare the phytochemical composition and antimicrobial efficacy between the seed and coat of *C. sinensis*.

B. BOTANY OF THE PLANT

Sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) (to distinguish it from closely related species like sour orange, *C. aurantium* C. reticulata and mandarin orange), is a small evergreen tree 7.5 m high and in some cases up to 15 m. It originated from southern China where it has been cultivated for many years, but is today grown commercially worldwide in tropical, semi-tropical and some warm temperate regions to become the most widely planted fruit tree in the world. Orange produces leathery and evergreen leaves of different shapes, ranging from elliptical to oblong to oval, 6.5-15 cm long and 2.5-9.5 cm wide, often bearing narrow wings on the petioles (Goudeau et al, 2008).

It bears fragrant white flowers either singly or in whorls of 6, about 5 cm wide, with 5 petals and 20-25 yellow stamens. The small, white or purple scented hermaphroditic flowers produce nectar for pollination by insects. The fruit, which may be globose to oval is 6.5 to 9.5 cm wide, and ripens to orange or yellow. Anatomically, the fruit consists of two distinct regions, the pericarp also called the peel, skin or rind, and the endocarp, or pulp and juice sacs. The skin consists of an epidermis of epicuticular wax with numerous small aromatic oil glands that gives it its particular smell. The quantity of wax is dependent on the variety, climatic conditions and growth rate. A plethora of microflora consisting mainly of fungus and bacteria are present on the skin and more copious in damp climates. This justifies the need for appropriate washing of the fruit before eating or proceeding to extract juice and essential oils. The pericarp consists of the outer flavedo, or epicarp largely made of parenchymatous cells and cuticle. Embedded oil glands create terpenoid aromatic compounds such as valencene, limonene, and alpha/beta sinesenal (Goudeau et al, 2008).

Fig.1: Image of Sweet Orange (*Citrus sinensis*)

Source: Wikipedia.Org. (2018)

Taxonomic Classification of Sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*)

Kingdom: Plantae
Phylum: Streptophyta
Class: Equisetopsida
Order: Sapindale
Family: Rutaceae
Genus: Citrus
Species: Citrus sinensis

C. ORANGES, HUMAN HEALTH, AND NUTRITION

The human diet contains important micronutrients namely vitamins C and E, carotenoids and flavonoids, essential for maintenance of human health. Multiple dietary sources of these compounds are present virtually in all plant material (Di Majo et al, 2005). The nutritional importance of foods is due to the presence of these functional food ingredients and antioxidant nutraceuticals or phytochemicals. Phytochemicals are present in edible fruits and vegetables and when eaten potentially modulate human metabolism in a favourable manner, thereby prevent chronic and degenerative diseases (Tripoli et al, 2007).

Increase in fruits and vegetables consumption protect against degenerative pathologies such as cancer andtherosclerosis (Keys, 2005); as epidemiological surveys had shown an inverse relationship between dietary flavonoid intake from citrus and cardiovascular diseases. Citrus fruits are the main source of important phytochemical nutrients and for long have been valued for their wholesome nutritious and antioxidant properties. It is scientifically proven that oranges being rich in vitamins and minerals have many health benefits. Moreover, it is now appreciated that other biologically active, non-nutrient compounds found in citrus fruits such as phytochemical antioxidants, soluble and insoluble dietary fibres are known to be helpful in reducing the risk for cancers, many chronic diseases like arthritis, obesity and coronary heart diseases.

1) **Medicinal Properties**

a) **As antioxidant:**

A high quality orange is one that is mature with good color intensity uniformly distributed over the surface. Such oranges must be firm with a fairly smooth texture and shape that is characteristic of the variety, free from decay, defects and other blemishes. The biological activity and the health effects of citrus flavonoids as antioxidants have been reported (Tripoli et al, 2007). These group of pigments as found in plants and together with anthocyanin play a role in flower and fruit coloration. Also, they are present in dietary fruits and vegetables and exercise their antioxidant activity in several ways, including the activities of metal chelation. Studies indicate that flavonoids are excellent radical-scavengers of the hydroxyl radical, due to their ability to inhibit the hydroxyl radical and donate hydrogen atom (Tripoli et al. 2007).

b) **Anti-inflammation:**

Citrus flavonoids contain compounds with anti-inflammatory activity due to the presence of regulatory enzymes (protein kinase C, phosphodiesterase, phospholipase, lipoxygenase, and cyclooxygenase) that control the formation of the biological mediators, responsible for the activation of endothelial cells and specialized cells involved in inflammation. Flavonoid inhibition of the immune and inflammation responses can be associated with their inhibition of these enzymes (Tripoli et al 2007). Indeed, citrus flavonoids are able to inhibit the kinases and phosphodiesterases essential for cellular signal transduction and activation. They also affect the activation of a number of cells involved in the immune response, including T and B lymphocytes (Manthey et al., 2001).

c) **Anti-Cancer and anti-Arteriosclerosis:**

Citrus flavonoids can prevent cancer through selective cytotoxicity, antiproliferative actions and apoptosis. Flavonoids are antimutagenic, thus protects the DNA from damage by their ability to absorb ultraviolet light (Stapleton and Walbot, 2004). They neutralize free radicals that promote mutations when they are generated near DNA. This has been shown in mice body irradiated with c-ray. Flavonoids can also protect the DNA by interacting directly with the tumoral agents, as in the induced chromosomal aberrations by bleomycin (Heo et al., 2004). The inhibitory effect of citrus flavonoids on tumoral development and cell proliferation by rat malignant cells, in cardiac and hepatic tissue of syngenic rats have been reported. The ability to function as such by citrus flavonoids are based on cell mobility inhibition. Oranges are also rich in iron, chlorine, manganese, zinc, sodium, phosphorous, iodine, calcium, folic acid, potassium, pectin, beta-carotene and amino acids and fibre.

d) **Anti-Obesity:**

Sweet oranges contain low calories and no saturated fats or cholesterol, but is rich in dietary fibre, pectin which is very effective in persons with obesity. Pectin as bulk laxative protects the mucous membrane from exposure to toxic substances, as well as by binding to cancer causing chemicals in the colon. Pectin has also been shown to reduce blood cholesterol levels by decreasing its re-absorption in the colon

by binding to bile acids in the colon (Walton et al. 2010). Orange peels contain the alkaloid synephrine, which reduces the production of cholesterol in the liver. The antioxidant elements in oranges combat oxidative stress that oxidizes the LDL (low-density lipoprotein) in the blood.

e) **Wholesome health:**

Oranges also contain very good amount of vitamin A, and other flavonoid antioxidants such as alpha and beta carotenes, beta-cryptoxanthin, zeaxanthin and lutein, compounds that have antioxidant properties. Vitamin A is necessary for maintaining healthy mucus membranes, skin and essential for vision. It is also a very good source of B complex vitamins such as thiamin, pyridoxine and folates. These vitamins are essential in the sense that body requires them from external sources to replenish. Orange fruit also contains a very good amount of minerals like potassium and calcium. Potassium in an important component of cell and body fluids helps control heart rate and blood pressure. Vitamin A also required for maintaining healthy mucus membranes and skin and is also essential for vision. Consumption of natural fruits rich in flavonoids helps body to protect from lung and oral cervical cancers (Stapleton and Walbot, 2004).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. **MATERIALS**

Seeds of *Citrus sinensis*, digital weighing scale, electric oven with thermometer, electric blender, knife, spatula, reagents, test tubes etc.

B. **COLLECTION OF PLANT MATERIAL**

Seeds of *Citrus sinensis* was collected from Nasarawa market. Nasarawa Local Government Area. Nasarawa State. Seed coat was prepared from Seeds of *Citrus sinensis* according to the protocol described previously by (Chethan and Malleshi 2007).

C. **PREPARATION OF POWDER**

The seed and coat of *Citrus sinensis* was dried under shade. The dried materials were mechanically powdered, sheaved using 80 meshes and stored in an airtight container. The powder materials were used for further phytochemical and antimicrobial analysis.

D. **PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICALS ANALYSIS PROCEDURES FOR BOTH SEED AND COAT EXTRACT OF CITRUS SINENSIS.**

Phytochemicals analysis was carried out according to the methods specified by Harborne, J.B. (1973). The phytochemicals analyzed was alkaloids, tannins, steroids, flavonoids, saponins and phenols. The following are the procedure for the analysis of phytochemicals:

1) Test for Tannins (Ferric Chloride Test):

0.5g of dried powdered sample was boiled in 10ml of distilled water separately in test tube and then filtered. A few drops of 0.1% of ferric chloride (FeCl₃) solution were added to the filtrate. Blue-black precipitate indicated the presence of Tannins.

2) Test for Alkaloids (Dragendorff's Test):

2ml of 1% Hydrochloric acid (HCl) was added to 5ml methanol extract and the solution were heated with stirring in a water bath for 10minutes. The cooled solution was filtered and a few drops of dragendorff's reagent was added. Reddish-brown precipitate indicates the presence of Alkaloid.

3) Test for Saponins (Foaming Test):

0.5g of dried powdered sample was stirred in 20ml of sterile distilled water and boiled in a water bath for 5minutes and filtered. 10ml of the filtrate was mixed with 5ml distilled water and shaken vigorously for a stable Persistent froth. The frothing was mixed with 3 drops of olive oil and shaken vigorously. The formation of stable foam, honey comb in shapes indicates the presence of saponins.

4) Test for Steroids:

0.5g of dried powdered plant sample was mixed with 10ml chloroform (CHCl₃) and filtered, then added 1ml acetic anhydride and few drops of concentrated Tetra-oxo-sulphate (vi) acid (H₂SO₄) to the filtrate. Green ring indicate the presence of steroids.

5) Test for Flavonoids (Shinoda's Test):

0.5g of dried powdered plant sample was boiled in 10ml methanol and filtered. Few drops of concentrated Hydrochloric acid (HCl) were carefully added to the filtrate. Red color indicates the presence of flavonoids.

6) Test for Phenols:

1ml of the extract was added to 10ml of 0.1% ferric chloride (FeCl₃) solution and was mixed together. The presence of blue precipitate indicates the presence of phenols.

E. ANTIMICROBIAL SCREENING**1) Susceptibility Testing of the Extracts:**

The antimicrobial activities of the methanol extract of seed and coat of citrus sinensis was determined against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Aspergillus niger*, which was collected from microbiology laboratory, Federal Polytechnic Nasarawa. The isolates were maintained on agar slant at 40C and subculture on a fresh appropriate agar plates for 24hours prior to any antimicrobial test. Mueller Hinton broth and Mueller Hilton agar were used in this study. All media were prepared according to manufacturer's recommendations. Mcfarlands turbidity standard scale number 0.5 was prepared to give turbid solution, normal saline was prepared, 10ml was dispensed to sterile test-tube and the test microbes was inoculates and incubated at 37oC for 6hours. Dilution of test microbe in the normal saline was done until the turbidity reached that of the Mcfarland scale by visual comparison at this point the test microbes has a concentration of about 1.5×10^8 cfe/ml.

The clinical isolates of the microorganisms were subjected to sensitivity test using agar well diffusion method. 5g of the extract was weighted and dissolved in 15ml of distilled water to obtain a concentration of 50mg/ml, and this was the initial concentration of the extract used to determine the antimicrobial activities from the extract. Mueller Hinton agar was the medium used as the growth for the test microbes, the medium was prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions, sterilized at 121oC for 15minutes using autoclave, allowed to cool and then poured into sterile petri-dishes to solidify.

After agar solidification, Mueller Hinton agar plates were swabbed with each test microbe using a sterile swab stick. The medium was punched with a standard cork borer of the 6mm diameter wells and filled with 0.1mg/ml of the test sample and allowed to diffuse at room temperature for 20minutes. Penicillin and Fluconazole was used as standards (positive controls) for bacteria and fungi isolates respectively. The plates were incubated at 37oC for 24hours and zone of inhibition diameter (ZID) formed around the wells were measured in millimeter (MM) using a transparent ruler (CLSI, 2009). All tests were done in triplicates and the growth inhibitory effect of the plant extract was recorded (CSLI, 2009) control plates made up of extract without inoculums and inoculums without extract was made in parallel.

2) Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC):

The minimum inhibitory concentration of the extract was carried out on the microorganisms that was sensitive to the extract and was determined using the broth dilution method. Mueller Hinton broth was prepared, 10ml dispensed into test tube and was sterilized at 121oC for 15minutes, and the broth was allowed to cool, Mcfarlands turbidity standard scale number 0.5 was prepared to give turbid solution, normal saline was prepared, 10ml was dispensed to sterile test tube and the test microbe was inoculated and incubated at 37oC for 6hours.

Dilution of the test microbe in the normal saline was done until the turbidity reached that of the Mcfarland scale by visual comparison at this point the test microbe has a concentration of about 1.5×10^8 cfe/ml. Two-fold serial dilution of the extract in the sterile broth was made to obtain the concentration of 100mg/ml, 50mg/ml, and 25mg/ml each. The initial concentration was obtained by dissolving 1g of the seed and coat of citrus sinensis extracts in 10ml of the sterile broth. Incubation was made at 37oC for 24hours after which the test tube was observed for turbidity (growth), the lowest concentration of the seed and coat of citrus sinensis extracts in the broth which shows no turbidity was recorded as MIC.

3) Minimum Microbiocidal Concentration (MMC):

The minimum microbiocidal concentration was determined to check whether the test microbes were killed or only the growth was inhibited. The nutrient agar was prepared, sterilized and poured into sterile petri-dishes and the plates were allowed to cool and solidify.

The content of the MIC in the serial dilution were then sub-cultured onto the prepared medium, incubation was made at 37oC for 24hours after which each plates was observed for colony growth. The MMC was the plate with the lowest

concentration of the extracts without colony growth (Hannan et al., 2014).

III. RESULTS

Table 1: Phytochemical screening methanolic seed and coat of *C. sinensis* extract

Phytochemical Constituents	<i>C. sinensis</i> seed	<i>C. sinensis</i> coat
Alkaloids	+	+
Steroids	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+
Saponins	+	+
Tannins	+	+
Phenols	+	+

Key: + Represent present
- Represent absent

The phytochemical screening of the methanolic extract of *C. sinensis* seed and coat revealed the presence of various bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and phenols. These findings suggest that *C. sinensis* possesses significant pharmacological potential due to the diverse biological activities associated with these phytochemicals.

Table 2: Antimicrobial activities of methanolic seed and coat extract of *C. Sinensis*

Microorganisms	Extract	Diameter zone of inhibition concentration (mm)/ Conc. of ext. in mg/ml				
		C1	C2	100	50	25
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Seed	NA	2.6	2.0	1.8	1.4
	Coat	NA	2.4	1.8	1.6	1.3
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Seed	2.8	NA	1.9	1.7	1.3
	Coat	2.6	NA	1.6	1.4	1.1
<i>Staphylococcus</i>	Seed	2.8	NA	2.0	1.8	1.4
<i>aureus</i>	Coat	2.7	NA	1.7	1.5	1.3

Key: C1 Antibacterial agent (Penicillin), C2= Antifungal agent (Fluconazole)

The results of antimicrobial activity of the extracts of seed and coat of citrus sinensis on *Aspergillus niger*, *Escherichia coli*, and *staphylococcus aureus* showed various degrees activities. The results of zone of inhibition of the seed extract of Citrus Sinensis against *Aspergillus Niger*, *Escherichia Coli* and *Staphylococcus Aureus* at 100mg/ml dose showed 2.0mm, 1.9mm, and 2.0mm at 100mg/ml concentration respectively as shown in table 2. The result of zone of inhibition of the coat extract of citrus sinensis against *Aspergillus Niger*, *Escherichia coli* and *staphylococcus Aureus* at 100mg/ml dose showed 1.8mm, 1.6mm, and 1.7mm respectively as shown in table 2.

Table 3: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of Methanolic Seed and Coat Extract of *C. Sinensis*

Microorganisms	Extract	Concentration of extracts (mg/ml)		
		100	50	25
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Seed	-	-	-
	Coat	-	-	+
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Seed	-	-	-
	Coat	-	-	+
<i>Staphylococcus</i>	Seed	-	-	-
<i>aureus</i>	Coat	-	-	+

Key: Absent of growth = -, Present of growth = +
MIC for seed 25mg/ml, MIC for coat 50mg/ml

The results showed that the seed and coat of citrus sinensis extracts has a minimum inhibitory concentration of 25mg/ml and 50mg/ml on *Aspergillus Niger*, *Escherichia Coli*, and *Staphylococcus Aureus* respectively shown in table 3.

Table 4: Minimum Microbial Concentration (MMC) of methanolic seed and coat extract of *C. Sinensis*

Microorganisms	Extract	Concentration of extracts (mg/ml)		
		100	50	25
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Seed	-	-	+
	Coat	-	+	+
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Seed	-	-	+
	Coat	-	+	+
<i>Staphylococcus</i>	Seed	-	-	+
<i>aureus</i>	Coat	-	+	+

Key: Absent of growth = -, Present of growth = +
MMC for seed 50mg/ml, MMC for coat 100mg/ml

The results showed that the seed and coat extracts of citrus sinensis is microbiocidal to *Aspergillus Niger*, *Escherichia Coli* and *Staphylococcus Aureus* at a concentration of 50mg/ml and 100mg/ml shown in table 4.

IV. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. DISCUSSION

The phytochemical screening of the methanolic extract of *C. sinensis* seed and coat revealed the presence of various bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and phenols. These findings suggest that *C. sinensis* possesses significant pharmacological potential due to the diverse biological activities associated with these phytochemicals. Alkaloids, for instance, are known for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic properties. Flavonoids are potent antioxidants that help in reducing oxidative stress and have been linked to cardiovascular protection (Patel et al., 2021). Similarly, tannins exhibit antimicrobial and astringent properties, while saponins contribute to immune-boosting and cholesterol-lowering effects (Zhao et al., 2019). The presence of these bioactive compounds in both the seed and coat of *C. sinensis* highlights

its potential use in pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications.

The study in table 2 evaluates the antimicrobial potential of methanolic extracts from the seed and coat of *C. sinensis* against *Aspergillus niger*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The methanolic extracts demonstrated limited antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*. The inhibition zones were smaller compared to Fluconazole (C2), a standard antifungal agent. At 100 mg/ml, the inhibition zone for the seed extract was 2.0 mm, while the coat extract showed a slightly lower inhibition of 1.8 mm. Both extracts showed antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* (Gram-negative) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive), with the seed extract exhibiting slightly better efficacy than the coat extract. The highest inhibition zone was observed against *S. aureus* at 100 mg/ml (2.0 mm for the seed extract and 1.7 mm for the coat extract). The extracts demonstrated weaker antibacterial activity compared to Penicillin (C1), which had an inhibition zone of 2.8 mm. However, the presence of inhibition suggests that *C. sinensis* contains bioactive compounds with antibacterial properties, possibly flavonoids, alkaloids, or phenolics, which have been previously documented for their antimicrobial effects (Goyal et al., 2020).

The lower activity against *E. coli* compared to *S. aureus* may be due to the structural differences between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. The outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria acts as a barrier, limiting the penetration of antimicrobial compounds. This trend is consistent with other plant extract studies where Gram-positive bacteria are generally more susceptible to bioactive plant compounds (Rao et al., 2022).

In table 3; the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) results from the methanolic seed and coat extracts of *C. sinensis* indicate varying degrees of antimicrobial activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The seed extract exhibited inhibition at 25 mg/mL, whereas the coat extract required a higher concentration (50 mg/mL) to inhibit microbial growth. This suggests that the seed extract has a stronger antimicrobial effect than the coat extract. The absence of growth (-) at 100 mg/mL and 50 mg/mL across all test organisms implies that both extracts are effective at higher concentrations. However, the presence of growth (+) at lower concentrations suggests that their antimicrobial efficacy is concentration-dependent.

In table 4; the seed extract showed an MMC of 50 mg/mL, indicating that concentrations below this level (25 mg/mL) were not sufficient to completely inhibit microbial growth. This suggests that bioactive compounds in the seed extract possess antimicrobial properties but require a minimum threshold concentration to be effective. Similarly, the coat extract exhibited an MMC of 100 mg/mL, implying that it is less potent compared to the seed extract. Among the tested microorganisms, *A. niger* was the most resistant, as growth was still observed at 50 mg/mL for the coat extract, while *E. coli* and *S. aureus* showed inhibition at higher concentrations. These findings suggest that fungal strains may require higher concentrations of plant extracts for effective inhibition, aligning with previous studies that reported fungal resistance

to plant-based antimicrobial agents due to their rigid cell wall composition (Silva et al., 2020).

B. CONCLUSION

The phytochemical screening of *C. sinensis* methanolic seed and coat extracts confirmed the presence of several bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and phenols. The presence of these phytochemicals indicates that *C. sinensis* could serve as a valuable source of medicinal compounds with potential applications in disease prevention and treatment. The methanolic seed and coat extracts of *C. sinensis* exhibit moderate antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, with slightly weaker activity against *A. niger*. The seed extract generally showed greater inhibition than the coat extract, suggesting that bioactive compounds are more concentrated in the seed. These findings support the potential use of *C. sinensis* extracts as a natural antimicrobial agent, though further studies are required to isolate and characterize the active compounds responsible for the observed effects. The study demonstrated that methanolic extracts of *C. sinensis* possess antimicrobial properties, with the seed extract being more effective than the coat extract. The MIC results indicate that the seed extract inhibited microbial growth at a lower concentration (25 mg/mL) than the coat extract (50 mg/mL), suggesting a higher concentration of active antimicrobial compounds in the seed. The seed extract was more potent than the coat extract, requiring a lower MMC. However, fungal resistance was observed at intermediate concentrations, indicating the need for higher extract concentrations to inhibit fungal growth completely.

C. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that further investigations be carried out to quantitatively analyze the phytochemical constituents present in *C. sinensis* seed and coat. In vitro and in vivo studies should be conducted to evaluate the biological activities and toxicity profiles of the extract to confirm its safety for medicinal use. Additionally, isolation and structural elucidation of the active compounds should be pursued to understand their mechanisms of action. Additional microbial testing should be performed on a wider range of pathogens, including Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, as well as other fungal species. Comparative studies with synthetic antibiotics should be carried out to determine the efficacy of *C. sinensis* extracts relative to standard antimicrobial agents. In vivo studies should be conducted to assess the safety and therapeutic potential of *C. sinensis* extracts for pharmaceutical applications.

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